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A Practical Reflectance Transformation Imaging Pipeline for Surface Characterization in Cultural Heritage

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Preview

- A flexible and portable **solution** for **image acquisition** with RTI, based on a low-cost hardware kit, flexible and easy to arrange in either a research lab or on-site.
- An image processing pipeline & **software tool**, with smart **per-pixel calibration**, outputting **per-pixel appearance profile**, upon which **material descriptors** (comparable with standard depth measuring system images) are extracted.
- The acquisition setup & **user interface** don't require expertise in computer science.

Motivation – Why RTI?

- **Reflectance Transformation Imaging** is an acknowledged technique for appearance and geometry acquisition.
- The study of the material characterization is important for the documentation of a cultural heritage artifact, as well as for modelling of dynamic effects such as aging.
- A CH objects needs to be studied from various perspectives based on a top-down approach, from surface attributes to the molecular structure of the material.
- Panoptical CH applications, (Duffy, 2013): paintings, numismatic collections, archaeological sites, fossils, rock art, ceramic vases .
- At the National Gallery, RTI was used for monitoring craquelure and deterioration of a painting support (Dessi, 2015).

Duffy, Sarah M. *Multi-light imaging for heritage applications*. Edited by David Jones, and Paul Backhouse. 2013

Dessi, R., C. Mannu, G. Rodriguez, G. Tanda, and M. Vanzi. "Recent improvements in photometric stereo for rock art 3D imaging." *Digital Applications in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage* 2, no. 2 (2015): 132-139..

RTI, briefly

- Records images from a fixed camera position of a fixed object scene under various incoming light directions.
- By means of light decoding, we can obtain more understanding of the CH object and decipher the employed artistic technique.

Main RTI Setups

PRE-CALIBRATED DOME WITH FIXED LIGHT POSITIONS

<http://www.worcesterart.org/>

VIRTUAL DOME CREATED BY FREELY MOVING A LIGHT SOURCE

<https://content.historicengland.org.uk>

Coping with non-ideal lighting

- There are mainly two types of RTI setups:
 - Pre-calibrated dome with fixed light positions.
 - **Free-form moving light source that requires light direction estimation** and is liable to inter-acquisitions difference.
- While more flexible, free-form lights imply **assumptions** about the light behaviour and the light-material interaction. Most common assumptions refer to a Lambertian material and infinite distant light source.
- (Xie, 2015) break the Lambertian assumption by considering a near-field lighting and the relation between scene irradiance and distance to the light source;
- (Giachetti, 2015) reduce light inhomogeneity using a white planar frame with constant reflectivity, but purely directional lighting.

XIE L., SONG Z., JIAO G., HUANG X., JIA K.: A practical means for calibrating an led-based photometric stereo system. *Optics and Lasers in Engineering* 64 (2015), 42–50.

GIACHETTI A., DAFFARA C., REGHELIN C., GOBBETTI E., PINTUS R.: Light calibration and quality assessment methods for reflectance transformation imaging applied to artworks' analysis. In *SPIE Optical Metrology* (2015), International Society for Optics and Photonics, pp. 95270B–95270B.

Fitting of the reflectance distribution data

- RTI transforms 2D image stacks into 2.5D multi-layer representations: **normal, albedo, texture.**
- Fitting functions:
 - First-order polynomial: Photometric Stereo (PS)
 - (Malzbender, 2001): Polynomial Texture Mapping (PTM)
 - (Wang, 2009): Hemispherical Harmonics (HSH)
 - (Pitard, 2015): Discrete Modal Decomposition (DMD)
- The higher the order, up to the limit of over-fitting, the higher the number of radiance phenomena taken into account .
- Classification?

MALZBENDER T., GELB D., WOLTERS H.: Polynomial texture maps. In Proceedings of the 28th annual conference on Computer graphics and interactive techniques (2001), ACM, pp. 519–528.

WANG O., GUNAWARDANE P., SCHER S., DAVIS J.: Material classification using brdf slices. In Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2009. CVPR 2009. IEEE Conference on (2009), IEEE, pp. 2805–2811.

Pitard, G., Le Goïc, G., Favrelière, H., Samper, S., Desage, S. F., & Pillet, M. (2015, June). Discrete Modal Decomposition for surface appearance modelling and rendering. In *SPIE Optical Metrology* (pp. 952523-952523). International Society for Optics and Photonics.

Our Approach

- Correct for the light inhomogeneity at pixel level, without any constraints on the light position or light form factor.
- Generate for each pixel an appearance profile composed by pixel light direction and pixel intensity value.
- Estimate geometry and reflectance parameters with a robust PTM fitting, using trimmed Least Squares method.
- Considers repeatability of acquisition.

Pipeline Overview

Camera Calibration

- **Radiometric** calibration: take pictures at multiple exposure and check if the brightness value is linearly proportional with the photons hitting the sensor.
- **Geometric** calibration: acquire images of a target with patches of known dimensions, from different camera poses, so as to cover the full surface of the sensor and compute intrinsic parameters and undistortion coefficients.

Acquisition Setup

- Digital camera
- Handheld and freely moved light source
- White planar background
- 4 black, reflective spheres
- Spectralon perfect white diffuser target
- Cultural Heritage objects

Acquisition Protocol

- Uniform sampling of the light → virtual dome
- No point light source approximation
- No distant light source assumption → close positioning of the user

Annotation and Light Calibration

- Semi-automatic pipeline
- Annotation of white planar surface > per-pixel light intensity correction
- Annotation of the glossy spheres > recovery of light direction from the highlights on the sphere -> interpolation -> per-pixel light direction
- The calibration of light intensity compensates for the spatial variance of the light, so that the pixel reflectance values remain photometrically consistent

Surface Characterization

- Extract stable and meaningful parameters from the low frequency signal, using a low-degree (biquadratic) polynomial interpolation.
- This part of the signal comprises both Lambertian and non-Lambertian diffuse components and is reliable for highly specular objects.
- (Drew, 2012) polynomial representation:

$$L = [a, b, c, d, e, f][l_x, l_y, l_z, l_x^2, l_x l_y, 1]^T$$

(a, b, c) – classic photometric stereo

(d, e) – interreflections, low frequency non – diffuse Lambertian signals
 f – ambient light term

- Outlier removal with Trimmed Least Squares (Rousseeuw, 2005)

DREW M. S., HEL-ORY, MALZBENDERT., HAJARI N.: Robust estimation of surface properties and interpolation of shadow/specularity components. *Image and Vision Computing* 30, 4 (2012), 317–331.

ROUSSEEUW P. J., LEROY A. M.: Robust regression and outlier detection, vol. 589. John Wiley & Sons, 2005.

Results

CH objects

Calibration

Acquisition

Repeatability and material characterization

Comparison with microprofilometer

Italian Bronzital, 1939
Nickel alloy

Italian Copper, 1931

Roman Quadrans, 9BC
Bronze

Silver plates: 95% silver, 5% copper

Silver
Sample 15

Polished; left side coated
with nitrocellulose wax

Silver
Sample 28

Chiselled

Silver
Sample 22

Chiselled

Silver
Sample 30

Chiselled

Camera Calibration

- DSLR Nikon D810
- CMOS sensor 36x24mm
- Full-frame lens AF-S FX Nikkor 50mm, f/1.8G
- Ground Sampling Distance 0.009 cm/pixel
- Brightness is a linear function of the exposure
- Images were corrected for radial distortion

Acquisition

- Camera settings: ISO 32, Aperture f8, shutter speed 0.8s
- Light source: LED (6500K)
- Stack of 49 images (4729 x 7380) in raw format (Nikon .NEF) : 12 azimuth locations with 4 corresponding elevation points.

Repeatability and characterization

- Repeated acquisitions;
- Robust Polynomial Texture Mapping fitting, discarding outliers -> stable reconstruction of descriptors;
- **Light intensity calibration improves meaningfully the quality of reconstructions**

Normal deviation

Without light calibration

With light calibration

-The median angular deviation of normal reconstruction decreases from 1.86 to 1.17 degrees for the Bronzital coin and from 2.69 to 1.41 degrees for the Roman quadrans.

Unsupervised Classification

- Two acquisition with different light sampling pattern of Silver Sample 15
- Goal: classify the coated from uncoated part
- 7-dimensional descriptors: albedo (color), PTM coefficients (texture roughness)
- Two-class k-means clustering

Without light calibration

With light calibration

Detail Enhancement

Original

Unsharp mask to
the normal field

Unsharp mask to the
PTM coefficients

Comparison with Microprofilometer

- Microprofilometer – standard measuring system for depth information with micron scale precision.
- Can be considered as ground-truth.
- Registration with similarity transform based on 12 manually selected control points.
- Quantitative : angular distances between the RTI derived normal maps with respect to the ground truth from the microprofilometer
- Qualitative : visual assessment

	Median angular distance (deg.)	
	Non-calibrated	Calibrated
Bronzital 10c	6.69	4.51
Copper 10c	3.89	3.03
Quadrans	9.77	6.17
Sample #22	7.07	3.53
Sample #28	10.45	5.44
Sample #30	14.60	5.56

Italian Bronzital

Italian Copper

Roman Quadrans

Silver Sample 22

Silver Sample 28

Silver Sample 30

Conclusions

- We proposed a practical pipeline for acquisition and processing of the freely moved light RTI, suitable for various Cultural Heritage Context
- Increased simplicity & flexibility of the RTI capture and processing
- Developed a custom software with friendly user interface
- Decrease the error in feature estimation by correcting for the illumination non-uniformity

This is just the beginning...

- Scan4Reco project due for 2 more years
<http://scan4reco.eu/scan4reco/>
- Aims
- Future work:
 - Include multispectral information
 - Explore the modified sensor, with removed IR cut-off filter
 - Add narrow-band filters
 - Spatio-temporal simulation by monitoring the change in the material descriptors (geometry and surface appearance)

**Questions?
Enlightments?**

Related Work

Acquisition protocols
Common assumptions about light and material
Fitting models

Our solution

Method overview
Camera calibration
Acquisition
Intensity Correction
Surface Characterization